

Kinetics and thermodynamics of fluoride ion sorption on fire clay from aqueous solution

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Abstract : The kinetics and thermodynamics of fluoride ions sorption on fire clay from aqueous solution have been investigated. The various factors that influence the defluoridation efficiency of the material were studied. Adsorption obeyed both Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Various thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated indicating that this system was a spontaneous one and endothermic in nature. FTIR studies showed the involvement of hydroxyl group on the surface in the adsorption interaction.

Keywords : Fluoride removal, fire clay, adsorption, Langmuir isotherm, kinetics.

Introduction

Fluoride is of much concern now-a-days because of its toxicity to human beings, livestock and plants¹. Excessive fluorides in drinking water may cause mottling of teeth or dental fluorosis and skeletal or bone fluorosis with its crippling effects². Numerous methods have been described for fluoride removal from water. The naturally occurring fire clay materials seemed to be an excellent one for the removal of fluoride from drinking water. In the present investigation it was planned to study fluoride adsorption capacity of clay minerals which are strong adsorbent materials under varied aqueous environmental conditions. The detailed investigation of adsorption studies by clay materials were conducted by batch method to determine the various effects on adsorption process.

Results and discussion

The defluoridation efficiency of fire clay was studied under different experimental conditions like contact time of the adsorbent for maximum defluoridation, particle size of the adsorbent, dose of the adsorbent, effect of pH and effect of temperature. Fig. 1 shows the defluoridation capacity of fire clay with time. The percentage of fluoride removed increased linearly in the early stages upto 50th min and thereafter remained static. Hence in all the experiments the time of contact of the adsorbent and adsorbate was fixed at 50 min. A similar type of study has been reported onto silicate minerals³. The defluoridation

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on the defluoridation capacity of fire clay.

experiments were conducted using fire clay with three different particle sizes viz. 75, 150 and 300 microns. The results are presented in Table 1 indicate a significant increase in defluoridation capacity with a decrease in particle size of fire clay. The defluoridation efficiency of the sample with 75 microns registered high defluoridation capacity due to larger surface area. The percentage of fluoride removed by different doses of fire clay is given in Fig. 2. The dose of adsorbent having the optimum

Table 1. Effect of particle size on the defluoridation capacity of fire clay

Sl. no.	Time (min)	Defluoridation capacity (F ⁻ mg/kg)		
		75 Microns	150 Microns	300 Microns
1.	10	616.0	467.0	400.0
2.	20	633.0	517.0	493.0
3.	30	667.0	567.0	540.0
4.	40	733.0	617.0	583.0
5.	50	867.0	700.0	640.0
6.	60	867.0	700.0	640.0
7.	90	867.0	700.0	640.0

Initial fluoride concentration = 3 mg/L
pH = 7

Fig. 2. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of fluoride.

fluoride removal efficiency was found to be 3 g. Further addition of higher doses of the adsorbents did not result in considerable increase in defluoridation. This is due to the overlapping of the active sites at higher concentrations of the adsorbents, thus reducing the net surface area⁴.

The percentage of fluoride removed at pH 3 is 99.0 and it has been observed that the same decrease with increase in pH. The influence of pH of the pronounced adsorption of fluoride on the surface of the material at low pH ranges leads to the assumption that chemisorption dominates within range and chemisorption along with adsorption occurs at higher pH ranges. The reduction in the percentage of adsorption of fluoride at higher pH levels is due to the increasing electrostatic repulsion between the negatively charged surface sites of the adsorbent and fluoride ions. The data are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of pH on the percentage of fluoride removed by fire clay

Sl. no.	pH	Percentage of fluoride removed
1.	3	99.0
2.	5	90.0
3.	7	87.0
4.	9	80.0
5.	10	60.0
6.	12	55.0

Adsorption studies were carried out at three different temperatures (303–323 K) keeping all other factors constant. The percentage of adsorption of fluoride ions at 50th min was found to be 87.0, 89.0 and 93.3 respectively at 303, 313 and 323 K (Fig. 3). The observation about the enhanced fluoride absorption rate by the adsorbent at higher temperatures are in perfect agreement with earlier findings. The adsorption of fluoride obeyed the Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms (figures not shown). The values of Q^0 and b were calculated and presented in Table 3. The increasing trends observed in

Fig. 3. Amount of fluoride adsorbed with time at different temperatures.

Table 3. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm constants at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	Q^0 (mg/g)	b (dm ³ /mg)	r	k	n	r
30	0.5385	5.8927	0.998	0.6587	1.9562	0.997
40	0.5621	6.7114	0.995	0.6670	2.3912	0.987
50	0.6119	9.5510	0.997	0.6759	3.1959	0.971

Q° and b confirm the enhanced adsorption at higher temperature. The values of n lie between 1 and 10 represent the beneficial adsorption and this agrees well with the observation of Traybal⁸. The endothermic nature of adsorption is indicated by an increase in K_0 with rise in the temperature. The negative values of ΔG° indicate the feasibility of the process and also the spontaneity of adsorption process. The value of ΔH° is positive (6.46 kJ/mol) and this indicates that the adsorption is endothermic. The positive value of ΔS° shows the increased randomness of the solid/solution interface during the adsorption of fluoride on fire clay.

The XRD data of the treated fire clay provided evidence of slight modification over the crystal cleavages (figures not shown). This is possible due to lattice dislocation in the crystal system. FTIR analysis of the sorbent surface before and after the sorption reaction has provided the information regarding the surface groups that might have participated and also about the surface sites at which sorption might have taken place. The shift of stretching frequency, corresponding to the presence of -OH groups from 3620 to 3510 cm^{-1} is assigned to the involvement of -OH groups in the fluoride adsorption process by fire clay.

Experimental

The fire clay was obtained from the sedimentary origin of thermal power station, Neyveli, Tamilnadu. It contains⁹ 30% Al_2O_3 , 52% SiO_2 , 15% Fe_2O_3 and oxides of calcium, magnesium and sodium. The sample was sieved to the particle size of 75 microns and was used without any pretreatment. Stock solution of sodium fluoride containing 3 mg/L were prepared and this was used in the

defluoridation experiments. The residual fluoride concentration in each sample was determined using the ion selective electrode, Orion ion analyzer, model, 94-09 USA. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters of the adsorption experiments were determined by conducting the experiments at 30, 40 and 50 °C. Detailed study on the adsorption of fluoride on fire clay has been carried out in our laboratory by varying contact time, particle size, dose of the material, pH and temperature. The mechanism of adsorption is explained using the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms models. The defluoridation capacity was calculated as follow,

$$\text{Defluoridation capacity} = \frac{\text{Amount of fluoride removed} \times 1000}{\text{Amount of adsorbent (g)}} \quad (\text{F}^- \text{ mg/kg})$$

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